

Economic Cost of Disease-related Malnutrition

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Abstract

Malnutrition is a condition that results from nutrient deficiency or overconsumption/ It is a condition that results from eating diets in which one or more nutrients are either not enough or are too much such that the diet causes health problems. It can be overnutrition or undernutrition. Disease-related malnutrition is the type of malnutrition that is triggered by illness or disease. Certain diseases and their treatments have a negative impact on nutrition. Disease-related malnutrition is a condition characterized by inadequate intake of energy, protein and /or micronutrient as a result of diverse number of diseases and their treatments. It is the primary reason for malnutrition in developed countries especially in the elderly since many of the diseases triggering malnutrition are related to age. It can affect individuals at any life stage including infants and children however, the prevalence is significantly higher in the elderly. The world prevalence of malnutrition is between 40-70%. Economic cost is referred to how much it cost to deal with consequences of problem. It includes opportunity cost and accounting cost. Economic cost of disease related malnutrition is both forgone opportunities and money it cost to deal with the consequences of disease-related malnutrition. The causes of disease-related malnutrition are of three aspects which are interlinked: increased nutritional requirement, reduced nutritional intake, and increased nutritional losses. Consequences can be physical, physiological and/or psychological. Economic cost of disease-related malnutrition is very high because is associated with an increase in morbidity and mortality, augmenting resources use and associated cost. Economic cost can be the additional health care cost, negative impact on social and economic development of countries, lost of income due to illness, reduced school performance and later earnings due to cognitive impairment and death. Pathways from malnutrition to economic cost are mortality, ill health, impaired physical growth and impaired cognitive development. In conclusion, malnutrition keeps people from reaching their potentials and disease-related malnutrition has a very high economic cost as malnourished adults are less able to work, contribute to local economies and provide care for their families.

Key words: Disease-related malnutrition, Malnutrition, Economic cost

Introduction

There are six types of nutrient our body needs in order to function properly: carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, minerals and water. The sufficient quantities and the balance of these nutrients are essential to maintain our health. The body uses these nutrients to provide energy for growth, for healing and for any physical or mental exercise in general. When it does not get enough nutrients or not in the right balance, it becomes malnourished.

Malnutrition refers to getting too little or too much of certain nutrients. Malnutrition is a condition that results from nutrient deficiency or overconsumption. It is a condition that results from eating a diet in which one or more nutrients are either not enough or are too much such that the diet causes health problems (FAO, 2013). Malnutrition is a state in which prolonged lack of one or more nutrients retards physical development or causes specific clinical disorders, such as, iron deficiency anemia, goiter, obesity, to list a few. Malnutrition can also be defined as an impairment of health resulting from a deficiency, excess or imbalance of nutrition. It also includes under nutrition and over nutrition.

Not enough nutrient is called undernutrition or undernourishment while too much is called overnutrition. Malnutrition is often used to specifically refer to undernutrition where an individual is not getting enough calories, protein, or micronutrients. It can lead to serious health issues, including stunted growth, eye problems, diabetes and heart disease. Malnutrition affects billions of people worldwide. Some populations have a high risk of developing certain types of malnutrition depending on their environment, lifestyle and resources.

According to FAO (2019), there were 821 million undernourished people in the world in 2018 (10.8% of the total population). This is a reduction of about 176 million people since 1990 when 23% were undernourished, but an increase of about 36 million since 2015, when 10.6% were undernourished. In 2012, it was estimated that another billion people had a lack of vitamins, and minerals. In 2015, protein-energy malnutrition was estimated to have resulted in 323,000 deaths—down from 510,000 deaths in 1990. Other nutritional deficiencies, which include iodine deficiency and iron deficiency anemia, result in another 83,000 deaths. In 2010, malnutrition was the cause of 1.4% of all disability adjusted life years (DALY). About a third of deaths in children are believed to be due to undernutrition, although the deaths are rarely labelled as such. In 2010, it was estimated to have contributed to about 1.5 million deaths in women and children, though some estimate the number may be greater than 3 million. An additional 165 million children were estimated to have stunted growth from malnutrition in 2013.

Undernutrition is more common in developing countries (FAO, 2012). Certain groups have higher rates of undernutrition, they include women particularly while pregnant or breastfeeding, children under five years of age, and the elderly. In the elderly, undernutrition becomes more common due to physical, psychological, social factors and disease which is a major cause of malnutrition (Schutz, 2002).

Disease-related malnutrition (DRM) is the type of malnutrition that is triggered by illness or disease. It is the primary reason for malnutrition in developed countries, especially in the elderly since many of the diseases triggering malnutrition are related to age (FAO, 2012). According to Schutz (2002), disease-related malnutrition is a specific type of malnutrition caused by a

coexisting disease. It is a condition characterized by inadequate intake of energy, protein, and/or micronutrients as a result of a diverse number of diseases or their treatment. Disease related malnutrition occurs when patients do not consume adequate quantities or quality of food from their diet or do not reach the right levels of nutrients to compensate for the specific nutritional needs created by the disease. Malnutrition is actually a cause just as much as a consequence of ill health: poor food intake, especially for a prolonged period, makes one more prone to illness and injury that can lead to a reduced nutrient intake.

Disease-related malnutrition can affect individuals at any life stage including infants and children however the prevalence of malnutrition is significantly higher in the elderly and particularly common in healthcare settings. One third of older people in hospital and more than one third of people living in care homes are considered to be at risk (Shekar, 2015). Several studies show the worldwide prevalence of malnutrition and at risk of malnutrition in hospitals is between 40-70%. Prevalence of disease-related malnutrition varied between countries; Philippines (73%), Canada (51%), Brazil (48%), Vietnam (33%), Singapore (29%) and Netherland (14%) (FAO, 2014).

Patients are at risk of malnutrition if they have chronic illnesses such as: cancer, alcohol and drug abuse, liver disease, pancreatitis, chronic kidney disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), congestive heart failure (CHF), dementia, Alzheimer's, Parkinsons, depression, anemia, and diabetic gastroparesis (Schutz, 2002). Also FAO (2012) noted that the most common diseases that can cause malnutrition include oncological diseases such as cancer, pulmonary diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) or cystic fibrosis (CF) and gastroenterological diseases such as inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and certain treatments of these diseases can also have a negative impact on nutrition, like chemotherapy or radiation therapy appetite through a wide variety of mechanisms resulting in poor food intake. Economic cost is referred to how much it costs to deal with consequences of a problem. Economic cost looks at the gains and losses of one course of action versus another; it does this in terms of time, money as well as resources. The term also includes determining the gains and losses that might have occurred by taking another course of action. Economic cost includes opportunity cost unlike accounting cost which only takes into account the amount of money spent. Economic cost is the accounting cost (explicit cost) plus the opportunity cost (implicit cost). Implicit cost refers to the monetary value of what is forgone because of choice made.

Economic cost of disease related malnutrition is therefore both forgone opportunities and money it cost to deal with consequences of disease related malnutrition.

Types of disease related malnutrition

European Society of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition (ESPEN) identify DRM as two categories; disease-specific inflammatory and non-inflammatory. DRM is divided into DRM with inflammation, which is a catabolic condition triggered by a disease-specific inflammatory response and DRM without inflammation linked mainly to non-inflammatory etiological mechanism.

Sub types of DRM with inflammation are chronic DRM with a milder inflammatory response (cancer cachexia and other disease-specific cachexia) and acute disease or injury-related malnutrition with a strong inflammatory response (Schutz, 2002).

Causes of diseases related malnutrition.

During illness patients tend to eat less than normal even though nutritional needs are higher as the body needs more energy to heal and recover. The loss of appetite generally comes down to several reasons. One of them might be the side-effects of treatment as different therapies or medicines may cause nausea and vomiting or require significant dietary restrictions. Depression could provide another reason for loss of appetite for it can make patients lose interest in food and eating in general. Pain can also be a cause because certain injuries make it painful to chew or to swallow.

Some patients have practical problems which prevent from them getting the right amount of nutrients, for instance preparing food and inserting it into the mouth in case of patients suffering from cachexia or Parkinson's disease.

Another cause of malnutrition lies in gastrointestinal problems, in other words impaired function of the stomach and the small and large intestines. Disease can reduce the efficiency of digestion, so nutrients are not converted into a usable form. In other cases nutrients may be expelled too soon for instance due to diarrhea. Such diseases include Chron's disease and ulcerative colitis.

After an injury, trauma or surgery there is an extremely high demand for nutrients in the body to repair the essential organs or tissues that are damaged in addition to its ordinary functions.

Thus, disease-related malnutrition comes down to 3 aspects which are interlinked: increased nutritional requirements (such as during an illness or after a trauma), reduced nutritional intake (due to pain, loss of interest or side-effects of treatment) and increased nutritional losses (due to malabsorption or diarrhoea) (Schutz, 2002)

Consequences of Disease Related Malnutrition.

The effect of malnutrition on disease prognosis is well established. Malnourished patients develop more complications, have a higher mortality rate, longer length of hospital stay and have a higher rate of readmission (Schutz, 2002). The consequences of disease related malnutrition can be physical, physiological or psychological.

Physical:

1. Weight loss, muscle loss, reduced strength and mobility , constant fatigue
2. Reduced fat and lean body mass, increase pressure sore risk.
3. Reduced ability to cough, increase risk of respiratory infections

Physiological:

1. Reduced gastro intestinal secretions, increased malabsorption
2. Impaired immune function, higher risk of infection/complications, longer recovery periods.
3. Impaired wound healing, increase convalescence.

Psychological:

Apathy and depression, decrease quality of life

If the diet does not provide for increased nutritional demand protein stores in the body are broken down to supply the required energy. This results in weight loss and a reduced quantity of muscles which in turn leads to physical weakness and vulnerability, thus patients are more likely to fall and be injured. Because the immune system is also weakened, there is a greater chance of infection. Malnourished patients tend to experience frequent illnesses with longer recovery periods as their body is less resilient. Wound healing takes longer too and so the time of convalescence increases resulting in longer hospital stays. Malnourished patients often need to be re-admitted to a healthcare facility or require on-going healthcare services after being discharged from hospital. They also tend to have a significantly higher number of total complications than well-nourished patients, for instance there is a higher risk of developing pneumonia and related mortality.

Sustained malnutrition may result in even more serious conditions, such as impaired functioning of the heart, lungs and gastrointestinal (GI) system. Weakness might turn into cachexia, a severe condition marked by weight loss, muscle loss, and general weakness in a scale that prevents patients from performing tasks on their own living an independent life.

In addition to all the physical and physiological consequences above there are negative psychological consequences to consider. Insufficient nutritional intake leads to constant fatigue and it might result in apathy and even depression

Cost of Disease Related Malnutrition

Disease related malnutrition is a serious medical condition which is associated with an increase in morbidity and mortality, augmenting resource use and associated costs. The burden of malnutrition is unacceptably high. Malnutrition is a universal issue that no country in the world can afford to overlook. According to FAO (2012), a third of reproductive-age women are anaemic, while 39% of the world's adults are overweight or obese and each year around 20 million babies are born underweight. Disease related malnutrition is common, affecting around 143,000 adults in the Republic of Ireland, with most of these individuals (93%) residing in the community (Schutz, 2002). Studies in adult malnourished patients have shown that the additional health care costs are about € 2 billion (€ 2000 million) per year

Beyond health, slow progress on malnutrition is also impacting the social and economic development of countries. It is estimated that malnutrition in all its forms could cost society up to US\$3.5 trillion per year, with overweight and obesity alone costing US\$500 billion per year. Obesity has health consequences but also economic ones. Treating obesity and obesity related conditions cost US economy about \$190 billion in 2005. A study estimated that the global economic impact of obesity in 2014 was \$2 trillion. This represented 2.8% of global GDP.

Malnutrition is responsible for more ill-health than any other cause. The health consequences of overweight and obesity contribute to an estimated four million deaths, while undernutrition explains around 45% of deaths among children under five. Poor nutrition carries a significant economic burden for individuals and entire economies. It is estimated that undernutrition,

micronutrient deficiencies and overweight at today's levels cost the global economy up to US\$3.5 trillion (FAO, 2013). This economic burden is a major impediment to government efforts to reduce poverty and to achieve targets such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The total additional direct medical costs of DRM in pediatric patients in 2013 were estimated to be € 51 million for acute malnutrition, € 46 million when focused on chronic malnutrition and € 80 million in case of overall malnourished children. This equals 5.6% of the total Dutch hospital costs for these hospitalized children. The total additional costs of managing adult patients with disease related malnutrition were estimated to be € 1.9 billion in 2011 which equals 2.1% of the total Dutch national health expenditure and 4.9% of the total costs of the health care sectors (FAO, 2013).

As well as the direct costs to the global economy of US\$3.5 trillion (FAO, 2013), additional costs of malnutrition are borne by families, in the form of higher medical bills, lost income including due to illness, reduced school performance and later earnings due to cognitive impairment. The various health and other risks associated with various forms of malnutrition vary by gender, age and context. Unfortunately, few data are collected at such disaggregation, making it very difficult to determine the cost and effectiveness of actions for specific groups of individuals. This remains a data gap that should be urgently closed. At the national level, costs include the rising bill associated with disability payments, while losses are squarely tied to lost economic productivity.

Pathways from malnutrition to economic cost

First is mortality. It is estimated that up to 45% of all preventable child deaths are attributable to under nutrition (Black, 2013). Severely undernourished children are up to nine times more likely to die than well-nourished children. Maternal mortality, linked to severe anaemia, and reduced adult life expectancy, linked to obesity and related health complications, are additional manifestations of nutrition-mortality linkages. Preventable mortality represents a loss of human capital that affects families and whole communities.

The second pathway is ill health. Treatment costs are borne by families as well as by health and insurance systems. For example, a full course of therapy to save the life of a severely wasted child costs between US\$100 and \$200 per child. In Ethiopia, the estimated national annual cost of undernutrition (treatment of 3 million underweight children) is US\$155 million, 90% of which is covered by families. At the same time, the per capita healthcare costs of treating obesity in the United States alone has been shown to be over 80% higher for severely or morbidly obese adults than for adults with a healthy weight. Focusing specifically on wasting, India's 45 to 50 million Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) lost to wasting translate to economic losses of more than US\$48 billion in lifetime lost productivity (where one DALY is valued at US\$1,000).

Third is impaired physical growth. Sub-optimal physical growth, often coupled with life-long susceptibility to illnesses, reduces economic productivity through lowered labour productivity or absenteeism from work. The losses to individuals from undernutrition in low-income countries have been estimated as 10% or more of lifetime earnings. The cost to low-income nations of productivity foregone due to undernutrition has been estimated in Uganda as 5% of GDP and in Ethiopia 16.5% GDP. Similarly, in high-income settings like the United States, job absenteeism

linked to obesity causes lost output equivalent to \$4.3 billion each year, costing employers US\$506 annually per obese worker.

The final pathway considered is impaired cognitive development. Poor nutrition from birth, continuing through school and adolescence, impairs cognitive development, delays school-attendance and reduces attainment, resulting in lost employment and socialisation opportunities throughout life. A multi-developing country study that explored the impact of impaired cognitive development on wages suggested that adults who were stunted as children receive almost 20% less in annual income than if they had not been stunted (Shultz, 2002).

Conclusion

Malnutrition keeps people from reaching their full potentials. Malnourished children underperform in school, limiting their future job opportunities. Malnourished adults are less able to work, contribute to local economies, and provide care for their families. Malnourished mothers are more likely to have underweight children, who will in turn have a higher risk of physical and cognitive impairment. This perpetuates a cycle of poverty and economic stagnation

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